

QUIZ**LAST NAME: VOLZ****FIRST NAME: TOBIAS****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSWord 360 on Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **Which of the following is, according to Kabiru Gulma and Laurent Cleenewerck, the correct definition of plagiarism?**

- Using a source of information while not giving credits to the author.¹**
- A method used to show where a piece of information came from.
- Plagiarism is using the exact words of an author.
- It is the idea that an author has produced on a topic but written in one's own words.

2. **According to the European Commission, which of the following is a correct rule for the use of the English language?**

- When using colons, the next word starts with a capital.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2019), 5.

- Colons should not be closed up to the preceding word.
 - One should not use colons at the end of headings.²**
 - An additional full stop is required if a sentence ends with an acronym that takes a point.
3. **Gulma and Cleenewerck describe various rules of thumb for writing papers. Which of the following is not one of these rules?**
- Do not make the paper clumsy.
 - Support assertions.
 - Try to write clearly.
 - State the central thesis of your paper at (or near) the end.³**
4. **Kate L. Turabian describes various ways to understand the kinds of sources readers expect one to use. Which of the following does she not mention in this regard?**
- Any legitimate source is helpful as long as the needed information is described.⁴**
 - One should consult primary sources for evidence.
 - One could read secondary sources to learn from other writers.
 - Reading tertiary sources for introductory overviews is helpful.

² European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 7th ed., 2011, 15.

³ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 14-16.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students & Researchers*. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. William, and the University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff., 8th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 24-25.

5. **Linda D. Bloomberg and Marie Volpe describe the structure of Ph.D. dissertations. According to them, which should be the second chapter?**
- Research methodology
 - Literature review⁵**
 - Presentation of findings
 - Personal introduction
6. **Gulma and Cleenwerck describe eleven important reminders concerning the literature review. Which of the following is incorrect?**
- One should omit needless words.
 - Writers should use the active voice unless one needs to use the passive.
 - One should use parallel construction to make a vital point and create a smooth flow.
 - Avoid using commas to bracket a phrase that is essential to a sentence's meaning.⁶**
7. **Complete the following sentence by Bloomberg and Volpe: Your dissertation is a project that extends over a period of time. Therefore, successful completion requires ...?**

⁵ Linda D. Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap From Beginning to End* (Thousand Oaks, California: SAGE Publications, 2008), 31.

⁶ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 17-18.

- Careful organization and planning.**⁷
 - Intellectual skills.
 - Family support.
 - Financial resources and a well-known Ph.D. dissertation advisor.
8. **According to Turabian, what should one keep in mind regarding a book's edition used as a reference?**
- One should always use the latest edition of a book.
 - The edition of the books is irrelevant.
 - Some books are published in more than one edition. Each edition differs in content or format or both. One needs to cite the edition one consulted, unless it is a first edition that is usually not labeled.**⁸
 - Some books are published in more than one edition. The content and format of each edition are usually similar.
9. **When identifying and developing a researchable topic, what should one, according to Bloomberg and Volpe, always keep in mind?**
- Audiences, length, and ethical questions.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, 3.

⁸ Turabian, 105.

- Religion, culture, and personal interest.
- The interest of the university, potential financial gains that might result from the research, and political considerations.
- The potential audience, intellectual value and worth of the study, professional and personal goals, and ethical considerations.⁹**

10. According to Gulma and Cleenewerck, which of the following sentences is spelled correctly?

- Its hard to understand him.
- The cat ate its food.¹⁰**
- You're hair looks great.
- Your looking beautiful.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda D., and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap From Beginning to End*. Thousand Oaks, California: SAGE Publications, 2008.

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⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, 7.

¹⁰ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 18-19.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.